

SYNTHESIS OF PIPERIDINE DERIVATIVES. PART II

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Diethyl 1-ethyl-2:6-diphenyl-4-oxo-4-ethyl (and 4-phenyl)-piperidine-3:5-dicarboxylates have been synthesised by the action of the appropriate Grignard reagent on diethyl 1-ethyl-2:6-diphenyl-4-piperidone-3:5-dicarboxylate. The high and the low melting varieties of the latter, mentioned by Petrenko-Kritschenko have now been shown to be keto and enol forms.

In a previous paper (this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 293) the preparation of four substituted N-methyl- γ -piperidols by the action of different alkyl or aryl magnesium halides on substituted N-methyl- γ -piperidones has been described. Considerable work in these lines has been done in recent years with unsubstituted N-alkyl-piperidones and the piperidols, thus obtained, and their esters have been examined for analgesic properties (John Lee *et al.*, *J. Organic Chem.*, 1947, 12, 885; Ziering *et al.*, *ibid.*, 894; Berger *et al.*, *ibid.*, 904; Ziering and Lee, *ibid.*, 911). In this paper the work has been extended for the preparation of substituted N-ethyl- γ -piperidols by the action of the appropriate Grignard reagent on diethyl 1-ethyl-2:6-diphenyl-4-piperidone-3:5-dicarboxylate (I).

II (R=Et) and III (R=Ph)

The action of *n*-butyl- and *n*-propylmagnesium bromides on the above piperidone was also tried but the end-product in both cases was a pasty mass which could neither be crystallised nor distilled in high vacuum.

The piperidone (I), used in these reactions, was first prepared by Petrenko-Kritschenko (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 3689) who obtained it in two distinct forms with different melting points (92° and $137-40^\circ$). He did not, however, offer any explanation of this phenomenon and just referred to these modifications as the higher and lower melting forms. The lower melting point form was obtained by the action of gaseous ethylamine on a cooled mixture of benzaldehyde and ethyl acetone-dicarboxylate. The higher melting point form resulted if liquid ethylamine was used. The present authors at first used ethylamine in alcoholic solution and the result was a mixture of both the forms which could be separated by careful fractional crystallisation from ethyl alcohol, the solubility of the lower melting form being greater. The present authors have further shown these to be keto-enol isomers, both forms being capable of separate stable existence.

(V, m. p. 92°)

The compound with the higher melting point has been shown to be the keto form (IV) by preparing its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. It does not decolorise bromine water and after two recrystallisations gives no coloration with ferric chloride in cold alcoholic solution.

The compound with the lower melting point, on the other hand, immediately gives a red coloration with ferric chloride and also rapidly decolorises bromine water, and is thus in all probability of the enol form (V).

A new synthesis of the well known analgesic, Dolantin, was undertaken according to the following scheme :—

But it was found that N-methyl- γ -piperidone (VI) was difficult to prepare, as starting from 85 g. of ethyl β -bromopropionate (prepared from ethylene chlorohydrin) only 7 g. of the piperidone (VI) could be obtained by the method of McElvain (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 1721; 1929, **51**, 922). This on reacting with phenylmagnesium bromide gave the desired piperidol (VII), but in an yield not sufficient for further reaction and characterisation. The proposed synthesis had perforce to be shelved pending the arrival of ethyl acrylate which would simplify the preparation of the piperidone (VI). Attempts to prepare this piperidone by the Mannich reaction from methylamine, formaldehyde and ethyl acetone-dicarboxylate did not succeed.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Diethyl 1-Ethyl-2:6-diphenyl-4-piperidone-3:5-dicarboxylate (I).—A mixture of ethyl acetone-dicarboxylate (14 g.) and freshly distilled benzaldehyde (7 g.) was strongly cooled in ice and salt and chilled anhydrous ethylamine (3.4 g.) added to it. The mixture was shaken for 15 minutes and then left overnight in the refrigerator. The next day the solid mass was filtered off with the addition of 30 c.c. of ice-cold ether and recrystallised from hot alcohol. m. p. 135–37°, yield 12 g.

When in the above preparation anhydrous ethylamine was substituted by a 30% alcoholic solution of ethylamine, the result was a mixture of the above keto form (I or IV) and the enol form (V). The pasty mass obtained was dissolved in the minimum quantity of boiling ethyl alcohol and filtered hot. The keto form separated on cooling and was collected at the pump and the enol form obtained by the slow evaporation of alcohol from the mother-liquor, m. p. 92°.

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of (I) was prepared in the usual manner from (I) and 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in absolute alcohol and concentrated sulphuric acid, m. p. 171°. (Found: N, 12.11. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_8\text{N}_5$ requires 11.80 per cent).

Diethyl 1-ethyl-2:6-diphenyl-4-oxy-4-phenylpiperidine-3:5-dicarboxylate (III) was prepared by the action of phenylmagnesium bromide [obtained from 0.24 g. (0.01 mole) magnesium and 1.6 g. (0.01 mole) bromobenzene in 50 c.c. dry ether in an atmosphere of nitrogen] on 4.2 g. (0.01 mole) of the piperidone (I) dissolved in dry ether. The experimental details were the same as described in the previous paper (Zaheer, Sen and Sidhu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **24**, 293). The Grignard complex was

decomposed by ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid and the piperidol (III) liberated was washed with a little cold ether to remove some diphenyl formed during the reaction. It was recrystallised from boiling alcohol in white leaflets, m. p. 151-52°, yield 2.5 g. (Found: N, 3.20. $C_{21}H_{23}O_5N$ requires N, 2.70 per cent).

Diethyl 1-ethyl-2:6-diphenyl-4-oxy-4-ethylpiperidine-3:5-dicarboxylate (II) was prepared as above by the action of ethylmagnesium iodide (obtained from 0.18 g. of magnesium and 1.2 g. ethyl iodide in 30 c.c. dry ether) on 3.0 g. of the piperidone (I). It crystallised as white leaflets from boiling alcohol, m. p. 142-43°, yield 2.0 g. (Found: 3.54, $C_{27}H_{33}O_5N$ requires N, 3.10 per cent).

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